

PERSONALITY AND ADJUSTMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Adjustment is a Continual Processes by which a person varies his behaviour to produce a whole harmonious relationship between himself and suggest that the word personality conveys a sense of consistency, internal causality, and personal distinctiveness. This issue of personal distinctiveness is very important. There are certain universal characteristics of the human race and particular features of individuals. We all for example experience stress and the elevated cortisol that goes with it, and we all suffer the immune suppressive effects thereof. But each of us is unique too. (Carver and Scheier, 2000)

Key Words: Personality and Adjustment

Need and Importance of the Study:

India is the all and only nation which gives importance of spiritual and moral aspects. Most of the nations turn their faces to India for guidance. The spiritual leaders in India, cultural and linguistic differences, unity and diversity are also able to catch the world's attention. This country is the birth place of a number of sages and is well known for its rich spiritual heritage. Modern age of science and technology has created certain evils. Industrialism, violence frustration, immorality self centeredness egoism narrow mindedness are rampant everywhere.

Personality plays an important place in the life of an individual. The right personality leads their life in a focused way. In the present day world adjusting with the environment is a most essential one. Adjusting with the fellow being will lead to better growth and development and also it leads to the development of a good personality. Hence the researcher is interested in studying the relationship between personality and adjustment.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out the level of adjustment among higher secondary Students.
- To find out the level of personality among higher secondary Students.
- To find out the significant difference if any between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their adjustment.
- To find out the significant difference if any among the higher secondary students of different religion with respect to their adjustment.
- To find out the significant difference if any among the higher secondary students of different community with respect to their adjustment.
- To find out the significant difference if any between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their adjustment.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- The level of Adjustment among higher secondary Students is high.
- The level of Personality among higher secondary Students is high.
- There is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary of students with respect to their adjustment.
- There is no significant difference among the higher secondary students of different religion with respect to their adjustment.
- There is no significant difference among the higher secondary students of different community with respect to their adjustment.
- There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their adjustment.

Related Studies:

Jyoti Tare, (2001) had compared the achievements of the students of urban and rural areas of Jabalpur Division by the traditional method of teaching with that of studying through branching frames of programmed learning in Chemistry Subject. Experimental and Control Group Design was used for the purpose of this study. 280 students were selected from different Government Higher Secondary Schools of urban and rural areas of Jabalpur Division. The achievement of the experimental group was found significantly greater than the achievement of the control group. The achievement of the urban girls through PLM was found significantly

higher than that of the urban boys. No significant difference was found in the achievement of boys and girls of rural areas in the post-test on atomic structure and chemical bonding. 135 boys out of 180 and 64 girls out of 99 wanted to continue the study with the PLM on both the topics.

Rekha B. Koul and Darrell L. Fisher (2004) reported the research into associations between students' cultural background and their perceptions of their teacher's interpersonal behaviour and classroom learning environment. A sample of 1021 students from 31 classes in seven co-educational private schools completed a survey including the Questionnaire on Teacher Interaction (QTI), the What Is Happening In this Class? (WIHIC) and a question relating to cultural background. Statistical analyses showed that the Kashmiri group of students perceived their classrooms and teacher interaction more positively than those from the other cultural groups identified in the study.

Subrahmanian, Upendran (2005) employed the qualitative case study using transcripts of email interviews with five participating teachers of English from a single urban, government aided college in south India. The interviews focused on the participants' views of teaching, teachers, language learning, teaching methods, students, and the media. Secondary data sources came from ten classroom observations made of the participants' classroom instruction. Data analysis was continuous; the beliefs of each participant were first identified before making cross case analysis. Findings indicated that there was a "disconnect" between the participants' stated beliefs and their classroom practices.

Table 1: Significant difference in Adjustment of higher secondary students on the basis of Gender
Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary students in their adjustment.

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Significant at 0.05 level
Male	116	96.11	12.04	9.54	Significant
Female	134	103.89	19.12		

Table exhibits the higher secondary students Adjustment on the basis of gender. The t-value is found to be 9.54 and it is greater than the table value of 1.96. Hence it is significant. Here null Hypothesis is rejected and research Hypothesis is accepted. To sum up boys and girls differ significantly in their Adjustment among higher secondary students.

Table 2: Significant difference in Adjustment of higher secondary students on the basis of religion
Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among the higher secondary students different religion adjustment.

Religion	Code	N	Mean	F-value	Significant at 0.05 level
Hindu	A	120	102.88	6.17	Significant
Christian	B	100	105.99		
Muslim	C	30	87.07		
Total		250	102.41		

Groups	Mean	SD	t-ratio	Level of Significance
A	102.88	42.42	1.02	Not Significant
B	105.99	47.82		
A	102.88	42.42	7.34	Significant
C	87.07	21.57		
B	105.99	47.82	6.98	Significant
C	87.07	21.57		

Table reveals the higher secondary students Adjustment on the basis of religion. The F-value is found to be 6.17 and it is greater than the table value of 3.00. Hence it is significant. Here null Hypothesis is rejected and research Hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is a significant variation among Hindu, Christian and Muslim students Adjustment. The mean scores of the three groups are compared by a t-ratio. The difference between the groups A and C, B and C are statistically significant at 0.05 level. Between the groups A and B are the difference is not significant.

Table 3: Significant difference in Adjustment of higher secondary students on the basis of community
Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among the higher secondary students of different community adjustment.

Community	Code	N	SD	F-value	Significant at 0.05 level
SC/ST	A	25	33.01	7.87	Significant
BC	B	75	58.33		
MBC	C	80	35.12		
OC	D	70	47.37		
Total		250	40.69		

Groups	Mean	SD	t-ratio	Level of Significance
A	101.48	33.01	0.45	Not Significant
B	105.62	58.33		
A	101.48	33.01	8.23	Significant
C	95.45	35.12		
A	101.48	33.01	5.38	Significant
D	108.07	47.37		
B	105.62	58.33	6.18	Significant
C	95.45	35.12		
B	105.62	58.33	1.29	Not Significant
D	108.07	47.37		
C	95.45	35.12	4.54	Significant
D	108.07	47.37		

Table shows the higher secondary students Adjustment on the basis of community. The F-value is found to be 7.87 and it is greater than the table value of 3.00. Hence it is significant. Here null Hypothesis is rejected and research Hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is a significant variation among SC/ST, BC, MBC and OC students Adjustment. The mean scores of the three groups are compared by a t-ratio. The difference between the groups A and C, A and D, B and C, C and D are statistically significant at 0.05 level. Between the groups A and B, B and D are the difference is not significant.

Table 4: Significant difference in Adjustment of higher secondary students on the basis of locality
Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary students adjustment.

Locality	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	F-value	Significant at 0.05 level
Rural	175	139.91	37.65	4.32	Significant
Urban	75	144.69	36.93		

Table reveals the higher secondary students Adjustment on the basis of locality. The t-value is found to be 4.32 and it is greater than the table value of 1.96. Hence it is significant. Here null Hypothesis is rejected and research Hypothesis is accepted. To sum up rural and urban differ significantly Adjustment among higher secondary students.

Findings of the Study:

- The level of Adjustment among higher secondary students is moderate.
- The level of Personality among higher secondary students is low.
- There is a significant difference between male and female higher secondary students with respect to adjustment.
- There is a significant difference among the higher secondary students different religion with respect to adjustment.
- There is a significant difference among the higher secondary students different community with respect to adjustment.
- There is a significant difference between rural and urban area higher secondary students with respect to adjustment.
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References:

1. Alfred P. Rovai. The relationships of communicator style, personality-based learning style, and classroom community among online graduate students. *The Internet and Higher Education*, Volume 6, Issue 4, 4th Quarter 2003, Pages 347-363
2. Christopher Murray, Kimber Malmgren. Implementing a teacher–student relationship program in a high-poverty urban school: Effects on social, emotional, and academic adjustment and lessons learned *Journal of School Psychology*, Volume 43, Issue 2, March–April 2005, Pages 137-152.
3. Compact Oxford Reference Dictionary (2001), Oxford University Press.
4. Lindner and Harris (1992) ‘Learning in education majors’. *The Journal of General Education*, Vol.47, No.1, 1998.
5. Melissa C. O’Connor. Sampo V. Paunonen. Big Five personality predictors of post-secondary academic performance. *Personality and Individual Differences*. Volume 43, Issue 5, October 2007, Pages 971–990
6. Patrick S. Y. Lau, Man Tak Yuen, Raymond M. C. Chan Do Demographic Characteristics Make a Difference to Burnout Among Hong Kong Secondary School Teachers?. *Social Indicators Research Series* Volume 25, 2005, pp 491-516

7. Patrick, H., et al. (2007). Early adolescents perceptions of the classroom social environment, motivational beliefs, and engagement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 99(1), 83-98.
8. System, *J Educ Psychol Consult* Volume 41, Issue 1, March 2007, Pages 149-163.